

TOUR GUIDE- GUIDE REQUIREMENTS

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Annotation: *This article is devoted to know minor features of the guide profession , personal qualities of the guide, requirements to his skills. And also guide's speech culture, stages of organization of guide activities, minor features of the guide profession.*

Key words : *Guide, guide profession, complex , multifaced, excursion service preparation, feelings of the guide, human qualities, skills, professional skills, excursion techniques, speech culture, external and internal speech, temperament of the guide, language style, guide to historical sites and monuments, guides of special types.*

“ Travel makes one modest. You see what a tiny place you occupy in the world.”

-Gustave Flaubert

“The World is a book and

Those who do not travel read only page.”

-Saint Augustine

Mathieson and Wall (1982) define tourism as follows:

“ The temporary movement of people to destinations outside their usual place of work and residence, the activities undertaken during their stay in those destinations, and the facilities created to cater to their needs.”

The guide's work wasn't considered a profession until the late 19th century, It was an amateur band for interesting exercises. The work of the guide was carried out by specialists in various fields inseparable from their main activities (teachers, museum researches, researches of the institute, etc...) Only a handful of tour guides and individual museums had guides in the state. But at that time, this activity began with professional characteristics.

The change in the function of the excursion service, its transformation from a form of recreation to an organizational work in working communities, to a network of public services. These reasons are increase in the role of a new speciality.

The formation of the guide personality occurs during the formation of the guide profession. The requirement for a guide's personality is that he or she adhere to general principles and norms of conduct and adhere to clear ideas.

The main qualities of a person include:

- Wisdom - acting intelligently;
- Responsibility - understanding the results of their actions;
- personal reputation - actions related to the protection of their rights;
- Individuality is the uniqueness of a person.

The guide should be able to demonstrate an active outlook on life based on the nature of his or her profession and use it in his or her daily activities.

Active life views are the participation of an individual in the life of society.

An individual's life views are reflected in his or her attitude toward society, labor, public and private property, other individuals, and the minority. In assessing the activity of an individual's life views, all types of collective, labor, ideological mass activity are taken into account. The main activity of the guide is to prepare and conduct a tour service.

Excursion service preparation is divided into 3 parts:

1. Preparation of individual text;
2. Remember the requirements of methodological development;
3. Remember the route.

Hearing the guide's story along the route, one can understand that it's some explains details a little, adds thoughts, gestures, from a smile. If a guide refers to written sources, the other is the subject enriching lions flow, one using document data, the other defines the break correctly. Guides with many years of experience will develop an individual approach to the tour and will use the methods they have used over the years in combination with other methods.

The authority of a guide is directly related to the problem of personality. The reputation of a guide depends on his knowledge, skills, abilities, ideology, experience based on this reputation stems from a combination of several factors:

- a. The prestige of the situation is that this guide is the tour guide guided by the tour guides. It is determined by the control of its activities;
- b. The reputation of his knowledge is that the topic of the tour is deeper than the tourists knowledge strengthens the reputation of the guide;
- c. Qualification reputation, experience in conducting excursions forms, the reputation of qualification (style of conducting excursions and techniques of applying the technique);
- d. An important foundation of a guide's reputation is his speech culture and nonverbal be able to use tools;
- g. interaction with tourists, creating the necessary environment in the group.

At the same time, his modesty, culture and speech are the basis of the guide's reputation. The basis of a guide's professional skills are his or her skill and knowledge. Qualification is the ability to perform certain actions using the knowledge and skills acquired by a person. Qualification is a conscious, automated component of behavior.

A skill is the ability to perform any element of it (under the minimum control of the mind) in the process of activity. Skills are formed in the process of goal-oriented activity.

Before developing a tourism product, it is useful to understand how the tourism system operates. The diagram shows the components involved.

In front of tourists, the guide can appear in the following cases:

- The informant, that is, the guide, only narrates an event, without expressing his attitude to the events, without explaining their essence, that informs the tourists about the knowledge;
- Interviewer, the guide plays the role of the interlocutor in the process of showing objects. The information is provided in the form of questions and answers, taking into account the views of tourists on the information, making the conversation interesting. The guide can add additional information to the story based on their relationship, questions;
- The commentator, the guide gives information about the observed objects, events, incidents and explains the reasons;
- The consultant, the guide, explains the object and advises on its correct viewing, helps the tourists to come to the necessary conclusions;
- An emotional leader, a guide analyzes objects and events, evaluates problems, communicates his feelings to tourists, observes an object or helps to understand the event.

Speech culture.

Speech etiquette determines a person's general morality. It is the main criterion. "Speech culture" means conveying the message that needs to be conveyed, with respect to the listener, with expressions that are appropriate to his or her mood and in a literary standard. Any unpleasant news can be conveyed to the listener without any hesitation. To do this, the tuner must know the language, the norms of literary language perfectly. A gentle, pleasant, polite setting doesn't even appear in small amounts. It is achieved

through conscious exercise from a young age, mastering the vocabulary of the language, imitating exemplary people in this regard, and organizing from them.

Speech is a means of communication between people who have a voice or a written form, demonstrating the ability of language. The use of language in speech allows the guide to express a set of specific knowledge on a particular topic. The comprehensibility, accuracy and expressiveness of speech for many factors, such as the correct choice of words, the structure of expressions.

Speech is divided into external and internal speech. External speech is communicative. It is important that its essence is heard and understood by other people. The guide's story is an example of external speech, and its mission. Influencing the consciousness and actions of tourists, about specific objects. It is the delivery of information. Language has two main functions: the transmission of knowledge, and explain the current situation. The function of language in the tour with the audience. In the process of communication, the transfer of knowledge is the verbal expression of feelings.

Each type of speech and the forms of speech that make up them constitute a separate genre of speech. Therefore, each genre has its main goal directions and a certain scope of influence, which is determined by nature. Each type of speech has its own main purpose. In particular, the main purpose of one-time speeches is to "win" the speech by influencing the audience. Aristotle wrote about this: There are three types of rhetoric, because the audience will be of the same type. Speech consists of three elements: the size of the speaker, the subject of the speech, and the person who is addressing; it is he (I mean the listener) who is the ultimate goal of all work.

Inner speech is the speech of a person's inner world, a pre-formation of ideas that need to be conveyed to the audience. When a person thinks about an object, he engages in dialogue with his inner voice. Thinks with the help of internal speech, in which he uses auxiliary tools such as drawings, images, tables. Inner speech is based on the knowledge a person has acquired. The guide repeats the content of the tour in full or in part in his imagination using internal speech. Each guide should make full use of the possibilities of internal speech by communicating by logical exercises. Language style is the diversity of language. The language of people's everyday life is different from the language of the official environment, the language of scientific abstracts is different from the language of secondary school teachers. There are the following styles of language: artistic, business setting (domestic), scientific, public, vocational.

The style of a guide's language is the verbal expression of ideas, the structure of speech. It is distinguished from other styles by its unique form and style in the story (for example: clarity, logic, imagery, expressiveness, emotionality, purity, richness of language, etc.) The individual style of a guide's language determines his or her level of professionalism, the culture of speech. The uniqueness of the guide language style depends on its functions:

- Restoration of the external picture of a historical event;
- The object being observed, the event being narrated, the natural phenomena

Tour guides assist people from all over the world. For this reason, it is vital to be able to communicate effectively. Tourists may come from various walks of life, age groups, cultures, nationalities, and backgrounds, or speak different languages. The ability to handle social norms and expectations is key to being an effective tour guide. The best guides are empathetic to cultural differences and prioritize making each delivery unique to their guests. Your tour guide should also have a sensitivity and understanding for accommodating those guests with special needs. One of the best ways to develop in any field is to watch experts work. When you examine the work of other tour guides, you can identify things they do participants enjoy and use that information to adjust your tours accordingly. Studying other tour guides may introduce you to ideas and techniques you have not seen before.

Conclusion. Every profession is a labor activity, a definite knowledge and labor from man requires skills. This knowledge and skills are derived from the process of general and special education as well as the daily practical activities of the employee.

In simple terms, a tourist is a person travelling to another location, away from their usual social environment, for business, pleasure or social reasons. When we think of tourism or guide, we think primarily of people who are visiting a particular place for sightseeing, visiting friends and relatives, taking a vacation, and having a good time.

Tour guides ensure that itineraries are met and that customers are being informed in an entertaining manner the location they are touring. They are also responsible for ensuring the safety of the group and ensuring that tour groups remain together. Tour guides are employed by tour companies, resorts and attractions.

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